

Helpless, But Not Hopeless

Kuruvilla Pandikattu SJ

Papal Seminary, Pune 411014

When we look around, O Lord, there is tension, fear and angst all around.

Tension as to the present and future

Fear of death and sadness of the impending doom

Angst about our very life: disconnected, separate and anxious.

O Lord, it is dreadful!

It is cruel, but it can be still worse.

None seems to know how it is and how it will end.

The doctors may guide us, but they too are not in control.

None is in control of the situation.

O Lord, it is unimaginable!

When we hear the stories of sudden and unexpected death,

Funeral where no one gets an opportunity to say bye properly

Easter celebrations with hardly any people around

Going around in masks and in distress.

O Lord, it is unbearable!

So many of us suffer intensely

From hunger, loneliness and emergencies

From not knowing what has happened to the beloved

255

256

From the sudden death of
the dear ones!

O Lord, it is terrible!

Is there an end to this?

How many will perish

before the end?

Who can measure the pain
and suffering

Of those who died and left behind?

O Lord, it is awful!

Even in our suffering

Some wants to make

Even our death

Is politicised for power!

How tragic Lord!

The situation looks hopeless!

Miserable and beyond future!

Precisely in these hopeless

Emerges Thy promise and our hope!

You are our hope, the only hope!

So, we want to trust in you.

For we have nowhere else to go!

None else to confide in!

You, you alone, have the words of eternal life.

O Lord, we long for it!

The life eternal that you promised

Can come even through depression and death.

Through pain and misery

Through our own cross!

O Lord, help us to surrender!

So, we want to hope, hope in
you!
In you we want to trust!
Help our lack of trust and hope!
You only can lift us up!
We want to trust in you.

The hope of all of us – humans and non-humans
The destiny of the universe
The future of ours
Lies in you and in you alone.
So helpless we are, hopeless we do not want to remain!